

USING ONLINE EDUCATION DURING SELF-STUDY HELPS TO INCREASE MOTIVATION OF STUDENTS FOR LEARNING ENGLISH

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***Abstract:** It is impossible to attract today`s youth without using various approaches those help for transferring of knowledge from expert to student is an art form and a skill.*

***Key words:** CLT, authority style, coach style, activity style, group style and blended style.*

According to the new reforms in Uzbekistan all Educational Establishments should train competitive, knowledgeable and skillful generation for our future [1]. In order to implement this reform, pedagogical staff should have not only deep knowledge on subject, but also they have to gain high-qualified pedagogical skills as well as with digital literacy. This features of the teachers sustain to provide for demonstrating proficiency in the subject area. If a teacher trains their learners with high preparation (it includes appropriate curriculum, syllabi and lesson plan), certainly these learners will be ready to competitive world and will be able to demonstrate confidently themselves in their field. But, the most language teachers have experienced the frustration of investing endless amounts of energy in their

learners and getting very little response. We have all had groups who never did their homework, who were reluctant to use the target language in pair or group work, who did not learn from their mistakes, who did not listen to each other, who did not use opportunities to learn outside the classroom, and so on. Therefore, the efficiency of teaching very much depends on learners` motivation, skills, and willingness or ability to cooperate and work as a community. These are also areas that we explore in this section in order to help learners realize how they can contribute to their to their learning. The first group of activities “Finding out about your various techniques of collecting information about the existing attitudes and knowledge of your students. Based on the collected information teacher can decide which are the areas where awareness rising is most needed, and which are the ones where you can move straight on to the practice stage. Activities should be appropriated to motivate students, also to help students realize and come to terms with the fact that difficulties are a natural part of learning. Therefore, gathered activities should be divided into three sections: “motivational stage”, “learning strategy”, “community building”. At the end of the sections, in “self-monitoring” teacher can find some examples of how to get students to think about their learning styles and make them aware that their group mates may have rather different preferences and use a variety of strategies. The introductory and follow-up part of the activities are especially important. In most cases it is useful to tell students what it is that they are going to experience and it is worthwhile to set aside some time for a follow-up discussion (if necessary, in the learners` native language) about what they discovered with the help of the activity. Teacher should ask some questions to get your students to talk. Some of the activities may surprise students and it is normal that at least partly from the realization what the teacher brought them. Sometimes the unusual organization or nature of the exercise attracts much

more attention than the awareness component, it has missed target. In this case teacher should put to use what have learnt about the expectations and previous experience of students and choose activities in which their attention would not be too much occupied by the novelty of the task. It is important to know what experiences learners have had and as a consequence what expectations they may have of their teacher. Also, information on learners` existing attitudes to learning and to the foreign language is the starting point for developing responsible attitudes. There are several ways to collect learners` needs and it is the best if the teacher teaches their students through their learners` needs., otherwise the students get bored and may not take their classes seriously. After taken needs they should be analyzed and all activities will be prepared for learners needs. Needs analyses should shape the content and the methodology of any effective ESP course. ESP is, in fact, an approach to language teaching based on the learner's reasons for learning and their language needs. Students can only conduct tasks and activities if the teacher gives clear instruction. Giving clear instructions teachers achieve an expected goal in a variety of instruction-given techniques that will enable them to set up activities faster, with more clarity, and with greater student involvement. It is also help to adapt and personalize to meet students` level and needs. Needs analysis is the systematic data collection and examining of all subjective and objective information required to describe and validate curriculum goals that support the language learning needs of learners within the context of the institutions that affect the learning and teaching situation (Brown, 2006) [2]. Needs analysis can help learners determine “what they know, what they can do, what they need to learn”. Therefore, needs analysis is the most importance for learners, and is generally viewed as a key part of the lesson. In other words, needs analysis involves seeking and clarifying information about learners` needs for language

courses, particularly regarding to what learners will be required to do with the foreign language in the target situation and how learners might best master the target language during the period of teaching. Specifically, it is also seen that speaking and listening skills are important for such students when building conversation or dialog specialists in their professional field. Furthermore, reading skills are also necessary for understanding specific content or instructions, while writing skills in connection with business correspondence. Through the influence of communicative language teaching, it has become widely accepted that communicative competence should be the goal of language education, central to good classroom practice. This is in contrast to previous views in which grammatical competence was commonly given top priority [3].

References

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